

THE IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION PROCESSES AND INFORMATIZATION ON YOUTH EDUCATION

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Annotation. The article talks about the various information influences exerted on the consciousness of young people in the context of globalization, their protection from the influence of various destructive ideas, the formation of a culture of information consumption and the tasks necessary for their implementation in the field of youth education.

Keywords: globalization, informatization, "mass culture," youth education, ideology, social networks, the Internet, mobile phones, information technology, religious extremism, terrorism, atmospheric and environmental pollution.

Introduction

We live in an intense and at the same time extremely complex time, which is changing at a rapid pace, radically different from the Times that humanity has experienced so far. Experts call this rapid period "the age of publicity" or "the age of globalization". In a matter of seconds, the people of the whole world find out about what happened on some edge of the Earth's surface. The ravages of globalization, which encompass both positive and negative aspects, have made the peoples of the world children of the mother planet. On the positive side, globalization covers the issues of ensuring the continuous cooperation of state bodies and business entities for the development of Science, the introduction of innovative ideas, technologies and developments, covering production and service in all spheres and industries with digital technologies, growing personnel with a deep grasp of modern knowledge, intellectual potential, creating an atmosphere of an "informed society" in the country.

On the negative side, now in conditions of unprecedented acceleration of information exchange on Earth, some "centers" are trying with all their might to take advantage of this and spread as widely as possible the influence of "mass culture", including the "charms" of Western life among other states and peoples. As a result of this, there are many cases when some individuals, whose ideology has not yet formed and an ideological gap has formed in their thinking, very quickly fall under the influence of such vices.

Today's globalization process is being given various definitions by experts. While some theorists say globalization is a positive process, some scientists recognize that it has many negative aspects. There is no doubt that in our country, the introduction into practice more of the positive aspects of the globalization process in the education and education of young people, as well as the protection against the influence of its negative aspects, will ensure a stable future.

In this case, it is necessary to further strengthen our National Information System in our country, to further strengthen the focus on issues of youth education. Our Zero President Sh.As Mirziyoev noted, " the upbringing of the younger generation has been important and relevant in all times. But in the 21st century in which we live, this issue is really becoming a

matter of life-matter. The more perfect the upbringing, the happier the people live," says the sages. In order for the upbringing to be perfect, it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to arise in this matter" .

Literature analysis and methodology.

Our country and foreign scientists conducting research on the impact of globalization processes and informatization on youth education have published many works on its essence, various informational influences on the minds of people in the context of globalization, protection of young people from the influence of various destructive ideas, tasks that need to be carried out in terms of youth education. In particular, Otamurodov S. from local scientists., Nazarov Q., Johraev N., Ergashev I., Abilov O', Mamashokirov S., Imomnazarov M., Erkaev A., Quranov M., Ochildiev A.S., Sa'dullaev D., Shermukhamedov S., Sultanov T., Tuychiev B.T., Kyrgyzboev M. Alimardonov T., Mukhtarov A., Abboskhojaev O., Umarova N., Ram R., Shaykhova H., Saifnazarov I., Saifnazarova F., Rahmatov O., Bekmurodov M., Ochildiev A., Umarova N., Usmankhojaev T.S., Salomov R.S., Solomzhanov K.M., Kholmukhamedov R.D. and others have done effective research in this direction. Of the foreign scientists, Bjezinsky Z., Chumakov A.N., Avdeeva R.F., Nisnevich Yu.A., Krylova I.A., Kuznesov Yu.P., Chistyakova S.S., Reisner P.R., Toffler E. and others have published works on the impact of globalization and informatization on their minds.

The study of the authors at the top shows that globalization processes are a complex phenomenon. Global problems-humanity their solution is associated with social progress and the survival of civilization. The authors insist that the main global problems of the present day are associated with the end of reserves due to religious extremism, terrorism, pollution of the atmosphere and environment, lack of rational use of Natural Resources, prevention of the negative impact of the scientific and technological revolution on humanity, improper use of social networks, ensuring human health, education.

Discussion

Today, the words " globalization "and" informatization " are among the most commonly used concepts. It is not for nothing, of course. After all, these concepts embody important features of the current period of the development of human and social life, including an extremely intense and complex reality, which is rapidly changing, radically different from the periods that human civilization has experienced to this day.

However, it should always be borne in mind that in today's ravages of globalization and information space, aspirations and actions aimed at threatening the nation, the national state, its independence and freedom, traditions and Customs, taking it into their own influence, ruling over it, using its wealth in their own interests, are inevitable to be preserved as a constant threat. Even being a little careless in the matter of youth education, especially in the context of today's globalization, can make our values created by our people for thousands of years go astray. Because the ravines of globalization do not know what limit Hecht is.

It should be noted that globalization in the modern era is going fiercely both in the field of Economics, in the field of politics, in the field of social life, and in the field of spirituality. Consequently, there is not a single country that is excluded from this process. Globalization means, first of all, development before our eyes, the problem of keeping the consciousness of the harmonious generation growing in such conditions from various spiritual threats is one of the main issues, despite the fact that progress is embodied.

At this point, the "positive aspects" of globalization are seen in cases such as increased relations between states, peoples, increased foreign investment, the creation of new jobs, the rapid spread of modern communications and Information Technology in the fields of Science and communication, helping people in different regions understand each other, helping in times of various stichic disasters. At the same time, the "negative aspects" of globalization – the emergence of environmental recessions as a result of the desire of transnational companies to get more profit, the formation of economic dysproportions in different regions, cases of certain mamakats remaining busy creating favorable conditions for the foreign market, depreciation of currencies of certain countries as a result of limiting the possibility of controlling financial flows, popularization. Indeed, in the context of globalization, "risks such as religious extremism, terrorism, drugs, human trafficking, illegal migration, "mass culture" have intensified, and humanity is undermining beliefs, family values that have been practiced for centuries."

The expansion of informatization in globalization processes leads to a further intensification of spiritual threats. This requires the absorption of spirituality into the minds of young people, a thoroughly thought-out systematic conduct of finding a way to the human soul, further intensifying activities in this area. When we talk about the issue of spiritual security in youth education, it is worth saying that the problem of researching the issue of the role of factors of national spiritual security, one of the important aspects of the topic of research, is becoming more relevant. It is difficult to pay special attention to the issues of raising intellectual potential in our youth, strengthening the understanding of the national identity in them, increasing the feelings of nationalism and patriotism.

It is no secret that today young people receive information extents from the media, first of all from "social networks" in the Internet system. The Internet, cell phones, information techniques – all this serves as the fruit of human intelligence, potential, for a person, to make his weight light, his limb close, but frankly, no Automata, machines, computers can replace a person, cannot be a spiritual feed on the soul, soul of a person. Our goal is not to give them up, but to maintain our self, our values, using them wisely.

The attention given to young people and the conditions created in our country are especially focused on the formation of a harmonious generation of reforms carried out in the field of education, the upbringing of young people who have their own independent opinion, can freely express their opinion, resist large-scale, foreign ideas, and the upbringing of a perfect person who can make his.

Therefore, it is necessary to constantly update programs, articles on education on sites that reflect our national and spiritual values created in our country. We believe that it is necessary to give more articles on the scientific, historical and philosophical heritage of the medieval eastern allomas and thinkers, whose outstanding contribution to the formation and development of modern science, such as astronomy, mathematics, geography, Geodesy, medicine, pharmacology, chemistry, mineralogy, in particular. This corresponds to the processes of complete transition to the new national model of Education, which, as defined by the Ministry of public education, is armed with modern scientific knowledge and serves to form a harmonious person. After all, only people with high scientific potential can ensure the prosperity of society.

Result

In the current period, when the globalization process is gaining momentum, it is necessary not to forget that only young people who are educated in modern ASNO, who can compete with their peers in developed countries of the world, who are physically and spiritually competent, can effectively use processes in the field of science, culture, education and ethics. An important aspect of the globalization process itself is that it boaberadies by expanding the scope of its ideological influence too much and accelerating immeasurably. Ideological globalization is associated with the development of the media and the revolution taking place in this area. Humanity is experiencing a new information revolution today, and it is not the first revolution in the history of human society. While the formation of speech has expanded the possibilities of information transmission, the emergence of writing has paved the way for its long storage and transmission of information over huge distances, even intertemporal, separating it from its creator. The establishment of the publication of newspapers and magazines further expanded the speed and inclusiveness in the transmission of written information. Radio and television, on the other hand, provided the transmission of information through sound and image, taking it to a new level of quality.

The expansion of informatization in globalization processes can lead to further intensification of spiritual threats. This requires the absorption of spirituality into the minds of young people, the systematic conduct of a thorough thought in every possible way to find a way to the human soul, to further intensify activities in this area. When we talk about the issue of spiritual security in youth education, it is worth saying that the problem of researching the issue of the role of factors of national spiritual security, one of the important aspects of the topic of research, is becoming more relevant. It is difficult to pay special attention to the issues of raising intellectual potential in our youth, strengthening the understanding of the national identity in them, increasing the feelings of nationalism and patriotism.

The life concepts and imaginations of young people who have no experience either are mainly formed by the media and the Internet. This makes it difficult for educational institutions to work. In the context of a large flow of information, a person must have an Information Culture in order to be able to feel free. In this place, when the information culture is called education, scientific knowledge and occurs during other types of activity, the systematized sum of knowledge, training and skills is understood, aimed at satisfying information needs.

The attempt to squeeze the national culture of the countries of the south and East by Western culture, the noise of harmful, unilateral information, the approach of two different standards under the slogans "human rights protection and democracy" and interference in the internal affairs of different countries, the existence of an attempt to create an unhealthy environment, the use of information technologies and tools to instill Especially spiritual threats to the minds and hearts of young people from the Internet system it is necessary for the protection of young people to become the work of the whole society.

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Suggestions and recommendations

First of all, it should be noted that globalization and informatization are an objective process, they are the product of the development of the intellectual potential of mankind, in this sense, they cannot be stopped by force. Therefore, following the enlightened path of protection under their influence can pay off. If the educational factor is applied at a positive level in the relationship between globalization and tolerance, then the possibility of the influence of national-spiritual and moral values on national development can expand. In such conditions, it is necessary to protect our national spiritual moral values from them, especially to instill in the minds and hearts of our youth the values of our spiritual heritage, to carry out the education system, the neighborhood and the tasks of each family itself.

In the context of globalization, the decisive factor in raising the culture of information consumption in our youth, the upbringing of the spiritually harmonious generation should be the disclosure of the true essence of Western "mass culture" and other negative influences, the identification and how to respond to them of the introduction into practice of the method of information psychological influence, which

Among the reasons for the penetration of young people into various streams is their knowledge, including their interest and desire to master religious sciences, and their trustworthiness, at once and for everything (wealth, fame, career, etc.).k.) should try to possess, singling out spiritual and spiritual factors such as maximalism in scientific terms. "Thou shalt be engaged in this organization, or in this task, in a special, honorable work, which not everyone can afford, and thou shalt become the saviour of the nation, of religion, of mankind, if necessary!", suggesting that the process of absorption of views is given particular attention to such characteristics. The main reason why they engage in this kind of work, hit axes in their own future, in general, get into the path of terrorism is that they do not have neither religious nor secular knowledge, do not know the attitude of pure Islam towards different streams.

In order to protect the spiritual world of the younger generation from destructive influences, the issue of what principles should be based on and what aspects should be paid attention to in the educational process should be the focus of all mentors, civil service, public and non-governmental organizations. In our opinion, in the context of globalization, a greater focus on the thinking education of young people is important in ensuring the inviolability of their spiritual world. Because, where high intelligence and contemplation prevail, then spirituality becomes a powerful force there.

In the era of globalization, where great struggles for the hearts and minds of people take place, strengthening attention to the upbringing of high spirituality, decency is an urgent task to educate the growing younger generation on the basis of religious and national values, to strengthen in their hearts a sense of affection for their people, their homeland, to warn them of information attacks of.

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